

The Role of Blockchain in Information Exchange

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Abstract— The advent of blockchain technology has improved the way data is stored and distributed around the network. Many industries, including banking, medical, manufacturing, and education, utilize blockchain applications to capitalize on the unique set of properties of this technology. Blockchain technology has the potential to improve trustworthiness, cooperation, organization, identity, credibility, and transparency. Due to the modernization era, many businesses have transformed the processes of information exchange. The use of digitalization for information exchange does reduce costs and save time. However, information exchange security has also been a concern. The transition of the digital information exchange system has created new opportunities for cybercriminals to attack. As a result, the integration of blockchain will directly eliminate cybercrime while also increasing the security level of information exchange.

Keywords—Blockchain, Security, Information exchange, Cybercrime, Data

I. INTRODUCTION

The rise of cyberattacks has been a huge problem along with the dynamic changes of technological advancement in this century. In tandem with technical innovation, cybercrime has grown exponentially. Cybercrimes have become one of the fastest-growing threats in the world [1]. As technology advances, so do the various types of cybercrime committed. Since then, it has progressed to the point where every information exchange in an organisation is vulnerable to cyberattacks in which an unauthorised individual has access to the data. Despite the implementation of security measures, organisations continue to experience more security events as a result of rising threats [2].

Integration of technology to support information exchange is heavily dependent on enabling an effective flow and process in business operations as it can reduce time and expenses. Many businesses have changed their norm to participate in an active role in using online integrated information exchange systems aligned with other fast-changing organizations [3]. Today, technology is utilised for a variety of purposes, but it is increasingly applied for the exchange of all forms of messages, papers, images, email, banking websites, and many more. With all of these technological capabilities and features, many individuals utilise information exchange channels to handle personal data, but many more are employed by corporations to display, distribute, and share information. Because of this, people and businesses alike are becoming more and more reliant on digital technology to support their critical business activities and handle highly sensitive and valuable personal and business data.

In comparison to technological advancement, the emergence of blockchain elevates the level of security in information exchange. Satoshi Nakamoto introduced blockchain in 2008 with the specific intention to serve as the public transaction ledger of the Bitcoin cryptocurrency [4]. However, in today's reality, blockchain functionality has expanded beyond that. Technology experts have discovered

numerous applications for blockchain in day-to-day operations. In addition to cryptocurrencies, blockchain has been widely used in asset and management tracking, payment processing, financial flow traceability, and, most significantly, securing information exchange. Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to describe the roles of blockchain technology in enhancing secure information exchange.

The paper is structured as follows: Sections two present a brief overview of blockchain technology and types of blockchain networks, respectively. Next, section three discusses secure information exchange. Furthermore, the roles of blockchain technology in enhancing secure information exchange discourse in section four. Section five supported the discussion by presenting two use cases of blockchain technology in ensuring secure information exchange. Finally, section six concludes the paper.

II. BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY

A. An Overview of Blockchain

Blockchain is part of Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), which records and shares data over several data warehouses, called ledgers, to accomplish its goals. The same data records will be handled and maintained by a network of distributed computer servers within this data warehouse, known as nodes [5]. For consumers of technology worldwide, blockchain represents a substantial advancement in the environment of information collection, dissemination, and governance. It can be described as a distributed database that is shared among the nodes of a computer network and is secured by cryptography algorithms and consensus mechanisms. It is a way to ensure that a transaction is valid without the need for a central authority. In other words, it is a system in which a record of transactions such as bitcoin or another cryptocurrency or any information exchange is maintained across several computers that are linked in a peer-to-peer network.

B. How Blockchain Works?

Essentially, the blockchain stores information electronically in a digital format that directly enhances the way technology users in today's modernized era. As a result, the structure of data in a blockchain differs from those of a traditional database. Technically, the blockchain will collect and group the data as blocks, each of which contains a collection or sets of information. When the block is filled with the specific information from the blockchain users, the blocks will be closed and connected to the preceding block, producing a data chain known as the blockchain. Each block also contains a hash key that further links to the previous and preceding blocks. When implemented in a decentralized nature, this data structure creates an irreversible data timeline.

Blockchain offers a decentralized approach in storing data or transactions [23]. It allows the data to be held in a database and spread among several network nodes at various locations and also maintains the fidelity of the data stored. If anyone

tries to change or alter the transaction that has been recorded, the other nodes in the chain are nearly impossible to change making it very difficult to alter thus preventing bad intentions. All other nodes would cross-reference each other, allowing the node with the wrong information to be easily identified. This system aids in the establishment of a precise and visible sequence of occurrences.

Figure 1. The basic operation of Blockchain technology [23]

Due to the decentralized approach, most blockchains are entirely open-source software. In other words, all transactions can be transparently viewed by either using a personal node or blockchain explorers, which let anybody to view real-time transactions. To secure the confidentiality of the data stored, blockchains are also encrypted. This implies that only the record's owner can decrypt it and expose their identity. As a result, blockchain users are able to maintain both anonymity and transparency. Thus, users of blockchain have their own public and private keys. The public and private key is a secret number, similar to a password, that is used in cryptography. The keys are also used in cryptocurrencies to sign transactions and establish ownership of a blockchain address.

C. Type of Blockchain

Current blockchain networks are categorized into four types: public, private, consortium, and hybrid blockchain [12].

Public blockchains offer a fully decentralized network in which every member may access the content of the blockchain and could potentially take part in the process of reaching consensus such as Bitcoin and Ethereum [13]. Public blockchains are mostly utilized for bitcoin exchange and mining. On these networks, nodes are mined for cryptocurrency by creating blocks for network transactions. This is accomplished by solving cryptographic equations.

Private blockchains, also known as managed blockchains, are permissioned blockchains that are administered by a single entity. The central authority chooses who can be a node in a private blockchain. Furthermore, the central authority does not always provide each node with identical rights to execute functions. Because public access to private blockchains is limited, they are only partially decentralized. Private blockchains include business-to-business virtual currency exchanges.

A consortium blockchain is a permissioned network that is exclusively accessible to a certain set of individuals. It functions as an auditable and consistently synchronised distributed database that maintains a record of the data transfers that take place between participants.

A hybrid blockchain combines the advantages of both a public and a private blockchain. As a result, a public

blockchain is used to make the ledger completely visible, while in the background, a private blockchain is running, which can regulate access to the alterations made in the ledger. Digital asset transactions and physical assets and agreements can all be managed with the use of the hybrid blockchain.

III. SECURE INFORMATION EXCHANGE

Repeated confidential information exchange activities are considerably vital to facilitate a day-to-day operation. This is due to the network nature of modernized industrial business and lifestyle. Information exchange has become one of the major activities for all organization across the globe. The information exchange can be best described as a process when one party intends to pass information to another party [10]. The bigger the size of the organization means the higher complexity and transmission of information within the internal or external parties of the organization.

A competitive business environment may produce thousands of confidential information such as customers' data, sales and purchases, and bank records on a daily basis in which the information will be transmitted from one authorized party to another authorized party. On the other hand, a single household may intend to purchase a luxurious car which requires paperwork between the dealership and the customer. Essentially, it requires confidential information such as proof of income, proof of insurance, and a driving licence to facilitate the agreement. Therefore, it proves that information exchange is highly important to cater to daily operations.

With the high velocity and volume of information transmission, the online information exchange method has dynamically changed from the traditional format to an electronic format. In other words, the exchange could be done electronically or through a certain system without handling a physical document from one person to another as the medium of exchange. Unfortunately, in parallel with the trend of high and critical dependencies on digitization for exchanging confidential information, its system is an exponential increase in illegal activities during the information exchange. This has increased the likelihood for an unauthorized person to intentionally form a cyberattack on the information exchange. Consequently, information is exposed to alteration and used for their personal goods.

According to [8], Microsoft released patches for 4 security holes in Exchange Server versions 2013-2019 after they discovered that hackers were aggressively exploiting vulnerabilities to gain total, remote control over the email systems of hundreds of thousands of organisations around the world. In addition, [16] states that in June 2020 Swissinfo.ch reported figures from the NCSC (National Cyber Security Centre) showing that there were 350 reported cases of cyberattacks.

Essentially, the security of information exchange has become a very hot issue in the digitalization era. Currently, information security is a critical asset for an organization to protect the information in their business [6]. Companies must take the necessary precautions to safeguard their most sensitive information against data breaches, unauthorized access, and other disruptive risks to secure the data. This is extremely crucial for information that needs to be exchanged from one party to another party. Lack of security information exchange can have consequences in the form of the business not being able to be conducted appropriately and efficiently.

IV. ROLES OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY IN ENHANCING SECURE INFORMATION EXCHANGE

The adoption of blockchain has tremendously left a significant impact on the information exchange system. Most importantly, blockchain technology is best known as a network of structured data with inherent security qualities. In relation to that, blockchain has a nearly endless amount of applications across almost every industry. Whereas each industry has the same common activities which are exchanging information. Aligning with the current important issue regarding the security of information exchange, the blockchain technology plays its role in this area as it can offer a more secure digital interface where the transaction of information is to be handled in a distributed network [7]. All the records in the blockchain are individually encrypted.

Encryption is a method of scrambling data so that only authorised parties can decipher it. Encryption adds another layer of security to the entire blockchain network process [8]. Essentially only the sender and the intended receiver of the information exchange are the only authorized person who can assess the information. Since there is no central authority in the blockchain, it does not mean that one can simply add, update or delete data on the network. Every piece of information on the blockchain is cryptographically hashed, which means that each piece of information has a unique identity on the network. Each block has its unique hash as well as the previous block's hash. The blocks are cryptographically linked together as a result of this property. Any attempt to change the data means changing all of the hash IDs, which is impossible. Thus, the integration of blockchain will certainly enhance the security of information exchange.

On top of that, blockchain offers a faster and safer transmission of information compared to the traditional information exchange system [21]. The traditional system is prone to many reasons for fallout like consuming time to process an exchange of information from one to another which directly increases the likelihood of corruption in the information. For example, in the healthcare industry, patients may fill in a requisite tangible form that includes the medical history of the patients. The form will then be sent to various departments to facilitate the whole operation and to enter into the hospital information database. However, during the process, an unauthorized person may take control of the form and alter the form for their own benefit. Such as an insurance agent will look into the medical record of the patients and offer an insurance contract for the profit of their organization. Thus, the blockchain system will facilitate the whole process as it uses an electronic context and eradicates a single government authority.

Most common information exchange systems are principally controlled by large corporations, this centralized feature control may raise privacy and security concerns as most individuals may abuse its power, which may result in the secondary use of the transmission of confidential information. Blockchain technology is growing and advancing every day, and it has a very promising future [18]. The transparency, trust, and temper proof characteristics have led to many positive impacts in terms of securing the information exchange system.

V. BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY USE CASES IN ENHANCING SECURE INFORMATION EXCHANGE

A. Health Information Exchange

Health Information Exchanges (HIE) are built up to provide a network where patients' medical records are shared with several healthcare facilities, enabling the data to be easily accessed by others in the same industry. In this industry, some of the treatments and diagnoses are not always determined by scientific evidence, as it may also depend on the doctor's judgment that may be influenced by their years of experience. This could result in treatment options and opinions differing from doctor to doctor, and patients receiving different doctors' recommendations for the same health problems. As mentioned by [14], 90% of treatment decisions depend on a patient's prior treatment, where previous medical data records and history play an important role in supporting quality care delivery.

Based on a peer-to-peer network of nodes, blockchain can remove the need for intermediary interactions and direct control by third parties in the process of exchanging information. Through blockchain features such as immutability and distributed ledger, it allows an efficient track record of access to sensitive medical data stored in the cloud. Therefore, healthcare organizations are able to make full use of blockchain technology in facilitating and advancing medical data sharing with other medical institutions while maintaining data accuracy and value due to its advanced security.

Blockchain technology will allow a strong, and secure control access to patients' medical records stored and processed in the cloud data platforms through cryptographic techniques. This could also reduce the risk of data being altered by different tending physicians or doctors which could cause medical mistreatment. Blockchain technology, which is based on a strong security platform, can detect and validate individuals who have access to sensitive medical records and keep track of all sharing actions, thereby improving the security of information exchange. Since the blockchain also operates on a peer-to-peer network, it has the ability to resolve technical issues such as security as it does not involve central authority. The decentralized network provided by blockchain technology can prevent the possibility of failure and security breaches.

B. Supply Chain Information Sharing

A supply chain includes many stakeholders, including suppliers, carriers, and customers. It is frequently complex because of the rapid development of economic globalization and intense market competition, which has resulted in fragmented information sharing within a supply chain. Blockchain technology can solve this problem by utilizing only a "single trusted ledger," which has the potential to reshape the element of data trust [15]. A supply chain management system requires the coordination of several parties to work in unison. Usage of blockchain offers transparency in ensuring the credibility and authenticity of the supply chain process [18].

One potential impact of deploying blockchain-enabled information sharing within a supply chain is that it ensures all members in the chain can obtain verified information which enhances collaborative partnerships [15]. Even though companies have access to the data of their supply chain partners, trust issues persist because they may intentionally or unintentionally mislead the supply chain partners with

inaccurate, incorrect, or counterfeit information that does not reflect the real data. Companies are looking for methods and plug & play tools that will allow them to securely share information while also checking the origin, authenticity, and integrity of data over time, allowing them to make more reliable and trustworthy plans and forecasts. Blockchain technology is an ideal solution to these issues because it creates a single, immutable record of data that can be viewed by anyone with access to it and that cannot be altered [22].

The decentralized nature of blockchain technology provides a high level of transparency, attracting interest from various industries to deploy this technology. Information sharing made possible by blockchain technology can improve teamwork in a variety of supply chains, including those in the construction, healthcare, and smart city industries.

C. Agri-Food Traceability

The food chain needs to become more sustainable to improve consumers' trust and purchase willingness. Tracking and authenticating information throughout the food supply chain is critical for identifying and addressing contamination sources, which contributes to agri-food chain sustainability management. Traceability is critical in food quality and safety management. Traditional traceability systems are based on the centralized server-client paradigm. Therefore, the stakeholders and consumers must rely on a single information point to store, transmit, and share the traceability information. Current food traceability systems are also ineffective at fostering trust among participants.

The practise and research of agrifood product traceability in the traceability chain have been significantly impacted by the blockchain. Blockchain technology enables the interchange of valuable information in the traceability management process and trust mechanisms for information security and transparency. The literature on blockchain-based traceability identifies the important impact on the agri-food supply chain, including transparency and accountability, traceability and fraud prevention, security and authentication cybersecurity and protection etc [24]. Therefore, blockchain technology has been acknowledged as a promising solution to address food traceability issues.

VI. CONCLUSION

In general, all organisations are advised to integrate the blockchain ledger into their system to create a solid information exchange system that improves security. The blockchain is much more secure than traditional record-keeping systems since each new transaction is encrypted and linked to the preceding transaction.

The decentralised and trustless nature of blockchain technology creates new opportunities, and benefits organisations by increasing transparency, security, and traceability.

Essentially, from medicine to finance, many sectors can benefit from incorporating blockchain into their infrastructure, which can directly improve security and information exchange.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Hussain, A. Mohamed, and S. Razali, "A review on cybersecurity: Challenges & emerging threats." In Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Networking, Information Systems & Security, 2020, pp. 1-7
- [2] K.K. Ishak, N.A.M. Razali, A.M. Lokman, and K. Toshiyuki, "Kansei information security assessment (KISA): characterizing trust as stimuli for user emotional assessment in information security". Indian Journal of Science and Technology, vol.9, 2016, pp 1-6
- [3] A.Tandon, P. Kaur, M. Mäntymäki, and A. Dhir, "Blockchain applications in management: A bibliometric analysis and literature review." Technological Forecasting and Social Change, vol. 166 (120649), 2021, pp. 1-19
- [4] S. Nakamoto, "Bitcoin: A peer-to-peer electronic cash system." Decentralized Business Review, 2008, p.21260.
- [5] A.G. Buja, M. Katan, N.M.H. Nasrijal, S.F.S. Alwi, and T.G. Siang, "Into the Look: Security Issues, Crypto-Hygiene, and Future Direction of Blockchain and Cryptocurrency for Beginners in Malaysia." in 2021 6th IEEE International Conference on Recent Advances and Innovations in Engineering (ICRAIE), vol. 6, 2021, pp. 1-6 IEEE.
- [6] N. Awang, G.N. Samy, N.H. Hassan, N. Maarop, P. Magalingam, and N. Kamaruddin, "Identification of information security threats using data mining approach in campus network." in Journal of Physics: Conference Series, vol. 1551(1), 2020, p. 012006). IOP Publishing.
- [7] R. Beck, and C. Müller-Bloch, "Blockchain as radical innovation: a framework for engaging with distributed ledgers as incumbent organization", 2012
- [8] D. Curtis, A. Togba., B. Lynch, D. Chaker, J.A. Perez, A. A. Lannyce, and K.A. Armstrong, 2021. At least 30,000 U.S. organizations newly hacked via holes in Microsoft's email software. Krebs on Security Retrieved June 20, 2022, from <https://krebsonsecurity.com/2021/03/at-least-30000-u-s-organizations-newly-hacked-via-holes-in-microsoftemail-software/>
- [9] E. Funk, J. Riddell, F. Ankel, and D. Cabrera, "Blockchain technology: a data framework to improve validity, trust, and accountability of information exchange in health professions education." Academic Medicine, vol. 93(12), 2018, pp.1791-1794.
- [10] A.S. Erri Pradeep, T.W. Yiu, and R. Amor, "Leveraging blockchain technology in a BIM workflow: A literature review." in International Conference on Smart Infrastructure and Construction 2019 (ICSIC) Driving data-informed decision-making, 2019, pp. 371-380. ICE Publishing.
- [11] J.J. Bambara, and P.R. Allen, "Blockchain: A practical guide to developing business", Law, and Technology Solutions, 2018, McGraw-Hill Education.
- [12] P.P. Ray, D. Dash, K. Salah, and N. Kumar, "Blockchain for IoT-based healthcare: background, consensus, platforms, and use cases." IEEE Systems Journal, vol. 15(1), 2020, pp.85-94.
- [13] G. Wood, "Ethereum: A secure decentralised generalised transaction ledger." Ethereum project yellow paper, vol. 151, 2014, pp.1-32.
- [14] A. Murugan, T. Chechare, B. Muruganantham, and S.G. Kumar, "Healthcare information exchange using blockchain technology." International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering, vol. 10(1), 2020, May, pp. 421
- [15] P.K. Wan, L. Huang, and H. Holtskog, "Blockchain-enabled information sharing within a supply chain: A systematic literature review." IEEE access, vol. 8, 2020, pp.49645-49656.
- [16] C. Nabe, "Impact of covid-19 on Cybersecurity." Deloitte Switzerland, 2020, December 15. Retrieved June 20, 2022, from <https://www2.deloitte.com/chen/pages/risk/articles/impac-covidcybersecurity.html>
- [17] Office, U. S. G. A. (2019, October 3). Science & Tech spotlight: Blockchain & Distributed Ledger Technologies. Science & Tech Spotlight: Blockchain & Distributed Ledger Technologies | U.S. GAO. Retrieved June 23, 2022, from <https://www.gao.gov/products/gao-19-704sp>
- [18] H.B.M. Hadzir, and F.H.B. Yusoff, "Blockchain Based Data Structure for Travel Entourage Tracking System." In 2019 4th International Conference on Information Systems and Computer Networks (ISCON) 2019, pp. 538-541. IEEE.
- [19] E.G. Spanakis, S. Sfakianakis, S. Bonomi, C. Ciccotelli, S. Magalini, and V. Sakkalis, "Emerging and Established Trends to Support Secure

- Health Information Exchange. *Frontiers in Digital Health*, vol. 3, 2021, p.636082.
- [20] S.K. Sharma, "A Framework of Big Data as Service Platform For Access Control & Privacy Protection Using Blockchain Network". *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, vol. 12(11), 2021, pp.476-485.
- [21] A. Thakur, "A Comprehensive Study of the Trends and Analysis of Distributed Ledger Technology and Blockchain Technology in the Healthcare Industry." *Front. Blockchain*, vol. 5, 2022, pp. 844834. doi: 10.3389/fbloc.
- [22] F. Longo, L. Nicoletti, A. Padovano, G. d'Atri, and M. Forte, "Blockchain-enabled supply chain: An experimental study." *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, vol. 136, 2019, pp.57-69.
- [23] M.S. Rahmana, M.A. Islamc, M.A. Uddinb, and G. Steac. "A Survey of Blockchain-Based IoT eHealthcare: Applications, Research Issues, and Challenges.", 2022
- [24] H. Feng, X. Wang, Y. Duan, J. Zhang, and X. Zhang. "Applying blockchain technology to improve agri-food traceability: A review of development methods, benefits and challenges." *Journal of cleaner production*. vol. 260, 2020, pp. 121031.